

The emergence of Celtic culture in Styria

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Abstract

The intensity of research into the La Tène Culture has increased in Styria (southern Austria), the Štajerska and Prekmurje (Slovenia) through recent archaeological excavations in Kleinklein and Lang, among other sites. The data from all later Iron Age cemeteries excavated in western Styria up to this point form the basis for a doctoral thesis which is mainly concerned with questions regarding the new Celtic population. This article presents a newly excavated burial from Lang/Schirka and discusses the context of other burials known from its vicinity. Together with the analysis of and comparison with results of Celtic settlement research in the Slovenian Štajerska, this allows us to gain new insights concerning the newly arrived populations.

Keywords

EARLY CELTS, STYRIA, LATE HALLSTATT, TRANSITION, GRAVES.

Résumé

L'intensité des recherches sur la culture de La Tène s'est accrue en Styrie (sud de l'Autriche), en Štajerska et Prekmurje (Slovénie) grâce à de récentes fouilles archéologiques à Kleinklein et Lang, entre autres sites. Les données de tous les cimetières de l'âge du Fer postérieurement fouillés jusqu'à présent dans l'ouest de la Styrie constituent la base d'une thèse de doctorat qui s'intéresse principalement aux questions concernant la nouvelle population celtique. Cet article présente une sépulture récemment fouillée de Lang/Schirka et discute le contexte d'autres sépultures connues dans ses environs. Avec l'analyse et la comparaison avec les résultats de la recherche sur les peuplements celtiques dans la Štajerska slovène, cela nous permet d'acquérir de nouvelles connaissances sur les populations nouvellement arrivées.

Mots-clés

PREMIERS CELTES, STYRIE, HALLSTATT TARDIF, TRANSITION, TOMBES.

Introduction

The settlement of 'Celts' in the area of modern Styria in Austria as well as the Stajerska in Slovenia has long been a central theme of research, with new insights having been gathered in recent years mainly through major development-led excavations like in Srednica/Ptuj, Nova tabla/Murska Sobota or Wohlsdorf/Styria. Current field research in Kleinklein and Lang has permitted to gather new information on aspects of on the emergence of 'Celtic Culture'.

Additionally, the publication of archival materials from the Archo Norico Burgmuseum Deutschlandsberg of several LT B2 burials in Lang, Unterpremstätten-Zettling and Dobl-Zwaring as well as the battlefield near Deutschfeistritz (Guštin 2017; Guštin 2020; Guštin and Božič 2019; Guštin and Kavur 2016), in combination with the excavation results from Lang and Kleinklein (Fig. 1), permits to address new topics and ideas about the La Tène period, which will be presented here.

Lang/Schirka, Burial 3 from Barrow 9

A La Tène cemetery, consisting of barrows and flat cremation burials, is known from a ridge in Lang/Schirka. The flat cremation burials, which have been known for quite some time, also included a chariot burial from the LT B2 to LT C1 transition and have been kept in storage in the Burgmuseum since the 1980s (Berndt and Bernhard 1998: 38–39; Bernhard 2012; Guštin 2021).

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Figure 1. Map of the mentioned sites of Early La Tène period in Styria (map by the author).

The excavations of 2021 provided new insights into the cemetery and grave inventories. In Barrow 9, which was systematically excavated, four cremation burials from the La Tène period were discovered around a large, centrally placed pit of the Lasinja Culture, with Burial 3 being the most interesting one.

Burial 3 was put down before the barrow was erected, which according to the central Burial 4 dates to LT C1 (Fig. 2). The burial pit is almost square with side lengths of 77 × 78cm and had rounded corners. Its fill contained a mix of fragmented pottery and remains of the funeral pyre, and also

Figure 2. Lang/Schirka, plan of the cemetery with plan of Tumulus 9, overview of the graves (image and plan by the author).

contained some metal finds. Underneath this deposit, an omphalos bowl was discovered which had been used as an urn for the cremated bones and which was partially covered and surrounded by the remains of other items of pottery, such as the neck of a flask. In the southern part of the pit a concentration of heavily burnt pottery could be identified which probably was deposited in an organic container, since in this area, a 25 × 50cm zone did not contain any pyre remains (Fig. 3). The burial's grave goods include a silver wire bracelet, a silver finger ring, two iron brooches of Münsingen type with differently ornamented feet, a ceramic bead and fragments of wheel-thrown pottery (Fig. 4).

The remarkable silver wire bracelet was produced during the early La Tène period (LT B) and is of a type that frequently appears in women's burials. The specimen from Lang belongs to Group 1 of wire bracelets after Guštin (2009: 478–479) that is distributed from the settlement area of the Helvetians along the Upper Danube area to the bend of the Danube, with the Lang specimen being the southernmost find of the eastern group. The plain silver ring of type AR-K2 after Bujna has parallels in Slovakian cemeteries (Bujna 2005: 80 fig. 64) and also in the cemetery of Mannersdorf am Leithagebirge in Lower Austria (Ramsl 2011: 109 fig. 79,22/3b). The iron brooches with plain bow and foot plate with organic application of Münsingen type can be identified as belonging to Type 1 B1 after Bujna (1998: 172–173 fig. 1,1B1) and are widely distributed across the Celtic world. The second brooch has a foot decoration in form of an acorn, with the shell fashioned from iron into which a round inlay, probably coral, is inserted.

The very interesting ceramic bead can possibly be compared with the beads used to decorate a brooch foot in woman's burial 1 in Michal na Žitovu in Slovakia. This burial assemblage also contained another five brooches, six bracelets, a hair pin and a few fragments of a belt and of pottery (Benadik 1962: 362 fig. 8,4). That burial can probably be dated to the transition from LT B1 to LT B2.

Figure 3. Lang/Schirka, Tumulus 9, Grave 3 (photograph and plan by the author).

Figure 4. Lang/Schirka, Tumulus 9, Grave 3: 1 silver bracelet, 2 silver fingerring, 3 iron fibula type Münsingen, 4 iron fibula, 5 ceramic object (drawings by the author).

The majority of pottery fragments from Burial 3 in Lang are still in the process of being restored due to their condition, but a few further interesting aspects could be recorded during excavation. The possible organic container already mentioned above exclusively contained coarse pottery. In the area where the remains of the pyre had been deposited in the northern part of the burial pit, fine pottery was recovered, which can be reconstructed as bowls, cups and flasks, and in a few cases as stemming from vessels with a conical neck (*Kegelhalsgefäße*). As already mentioned, the urn was an omphalos bowl.

The beginning of Celtic Culture in Styria

In northern Styria, the earliest La Tène/Celtic finds of phases LT A and LT B1 must be considered to be isolated single finds in settlement contexts. Among them are the sword chape from Kainischtraun, the fragment of a beaked flagon from the Kulm near Aigen im Ennstal or also the pottery finds from Kaiserköpperl near Rottenmann (Tiefengraber 2015: 598–602), as well as the bronze belt hook from the Ausseerland (Modl 2021). In central Styria, bronze brooches from phase LT B1 are known from the Kulm near Weiz, the Königsberg near Tieschen and the Dietenberg near Ligist (Tiefengraber 2015: 601–602).

‘Celtic’ settlement activity in Styria only properly starts in phase LT B2, with the cemeteries from Lang, Unterpremstätten-Zettling and Dobl Zwaring and a single burial from Graz. The complete period of La Tène/Celtic settlement can be observed in the cemeteries of Lang and Kleinklein, which are continually used from the early to the late La Tène period.

Next to the famous Hallstatt period barrow of the Pommerkogel at the foot of the Burgstallkogel near Kleinklein (Egg and Kramer 2016), a La Tène warrior burial was excavated in the 1980s (Dobiat 1996). Further excavations in 2019–2020 discovered another 13 La Tène burials (Fig. 5). The cremation burials were partially affected by agricultural activity, resulting in variable states of preservation. Seven burials contain weapons in the form of swords with scabbards, spearheads or knives. All burials contain dress components and/or jewellery but little pottery. Fragments of bronze hollow buckle anklets and of an iron knot ring, which either was a bracelet or a torc, seem particularly noteworthy. During the excavations, remains of organic containers for the burnt bone and traces of wooden grave constructions could be recorded.

In Burial 1, a sword with richly decorated scabbard and remains of a belt chain, a spearhead and fragments of a shield rim fitting were found. Apart from these, there were also remains of an iron brooch, an iron razor and three urns in this burial. All these finds can be dated to the end of LT B2 (Dobiat 1996). The start of this cemetery in the early LT B2 phase is marked by Burial 2, which contained a sword of Kosd C type, a spearhead with a narrow, elongated blade, a knife and three early La Tène scheme brooches. In addition, a bronze and an iron ring could be recovered, which probably were attaching the sword to the belt suspension, and a few fragments of pottery (Mauthner 2022).

Another two early La Tène burials from the vicinity of Unterpremstätten and Dobl-Zwaring have already been published. Both contained a sword of Hatvan-Boldog type and an early La Tène scheme brooch, with the latter also containing a nail with a swastika decoration. The former also contained a knife, two bowls and a *Kegelhalsgefäß* (Guštin and Kavur 2016).

An important cemetery was excavated in Wohlsdorf during the construction of the Koralmbahn. This cemetery consists of 13 burials, with a preliminary report already published. These burials date to the transition from LT B2 to LT C1 (Szilasi 2015).

On the Kugelstein, a ridge overlooking the Mur valley near Deutschfeistritz, a large number of weapon finds were made which date to the early La Tène period. These include spearheads, swords,

Figure 5. Kleinklein, Celtic cemetery next to burial mound 'Pommerkogel' (photograph by H. Vrabec).

belt chains, shield bosses and brooches and a few tools, scattered across an area of $2,3 \times 0,8$ km. Due to their preservation – many objects are broken into pieces – an interpretation as a battlefield seems justified. The finds date from LT B2 to the turn to LT C1 and indicate that the battle took place around 300 BC (Guštin 2017; Guštin and Božič 2019; Tiefengraber and Hebert 2021).

In the neighbouring region of northern Slovenia, the Stajerska, Celtic burials were discovered during motorway development. In Srednica near Ptuj, a few prehistoric features were excavated, including – besides houses from the Chalcolithic and remains of Hallstatt period buildings – a cemetery containing 27 Hallstatt barrows. Into one of these, four burials were inserted in the La Tène period. Inhumation burials 4, 6 and 7 were women's graves with necklaces, bracelets and bronze as well as iron brooches. Cremation grave 9 contained a warrior who had been buried with a sword, spearhead, knife and brooches as well as pottery fragments. These burials date to phases LT B2 and LT C (Lubšina-Tušek and Kavur 2011).

Another small cemetery with three burials was excavated in Orehova vas near Maribor, with a cremation of a woman and two weapon burials. One of the latter, Grave 3, was a double burial containing an inhumation of a woman in addition to the cremated warrior (Grahek 2015).

Discussion

The turn from the late Hallstatt (Ha D2/3) to the early La Tène period in the eastern Alps is difficult to identify. The phases preceding the early La Tène period can hardly be identified in the archaeological record, except perhaps the burials from Bergla, which can be dated to the Ha D2/3 phases due to bead and pottery finds and which seem to be the latest Hallstatt culture burials in Styria (Artner 2007). A comparatively sparse occupation can also be expected in Štajerska to the south, where sparse remains are known from Rifnik and the vicinity of Celje (Mele 2012: 153).

Evidence for the burial practice in the La Tène cemeteries of western Styria to date consists exclusively of cremation graves. This is noteworthy, since in the larger cemeteries in Lower Austria like Mannersdorf or Pottenbrunn, both inhumation and cremation were practised. In Srednica near Ptuj, the LT B2 burials indicate a similar mixed practice with three inhumations and one cremation grave (Kavur and Lubšina-Tušek 2016). An interesting aspect of burial practice is the ‘culture of memory’ indicated by the reuse of old cemeteries and barrows, which can repeatedly be observed in the south-eastern Alps. The cases in Kleinklein around the Pommerkogel and those also already mentioned in Srednica near Ptuj (Fig. 6) seem to imply this (Mauthner forthcoming), with further examples from the Gracarca in Carinthia (Gleirscher 2009: 144-145) and a few sites in Slovenia supporting this suggestion (Guštin *et al.* 2017).

Figure 6. Srednica near Ptuj, plan of the cemetery with Celtic graves (after Kavur and Lubšina-Tušek 2016: fig. 11).

A particularly important burial for the early La Tène culture in Styria is Burial 3 of Barrow 9 on the cemetery of Lang/Schirka. The silver bracelet and silver finger ring are comparable to finds from La Tène period cemeteries in Slovakia. Also exceptional is the iron brooch with the remarkable foot decoration in the form of an iron acorn filled with another material, possibly coral. Due to the amount of finds in it, the burial can be dated to phase LT B1c, i.e. the end of the 4th century BC.

In this context it must also be considered whether Hallstatt period traditions continued, as has already been suggested for neighbouring Carinthia (Gleirscher 2005: 106). On the one hand, the La Tène period Barrow 9 from Lang/Schirka might indicate that Hallstatt burial traditions continued. Also, Burial 3, with its burial rite including the deposition in the grave of pyre remains and (fragmented) pottery, may also well be following Hallstatt period practices. On the other hand, it might also be possible that another change in customs and traditions at the end of the Hallstatt period resulted in material culture leaving no identifiable traces in the archaeological record, creating an apparent hiatus due to an ‘evidence filter’ between the late Hallstatt period and the final stages of the early La Tène period. With the cemetery of Bergla (Artner 2007), already mentioned above, and the possibly late Hallstatt/early La Tène transition period finds and features from the Bubenberg/Hoarachkogel (Berndt and Bernhard 1998: 38–39), which are still awaiting proper assessment and analysis, more light could possibly be shed in the next few years on this archaeologically barely traceable period.

The research conducted over the last few years has already significantly improved the picture of the early La Tène period in Styria and the Stajerska, with the cemeteries demonstrating a once more archaeologically observable, quite dense occupation in the phase LT B2 (end of 4th / beginning of 3rd century BC).

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